

“THE NOTIONS OF SLANG AND JARGON IN ENGLISH”

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It is said that slang is not a harmful language, but rather a necessary part of the system of modern speech. It is constantly changing, evolving, and can be instantly formed and disappear forever. All changes in the language associated with the appearance of slang are based on the simplification and understanding of spoken language. Slang itself is a living and dynamic system that is used in various areas of human life. This can be in many different areas of culture. After all, in recent times, almost no one and nothing can do without some so-called "slang". From foreign works, in particular V.Burke's reference book, which is indicative, characterizes literature at almost all levels of General speech. He wrote: "Slang was invented as an antidote to grammar. The rigid school formalism was softened by the frivolous and sometimes obscene democracy of street slang, that eccentric and undisciplined language of disrespectful youth. It is difficult to disagree with the opinion of V.Burke, since "slang" can be called a completely obscene speech that is used in everyday life. But it is absolutely useless to fight it, because it becomes clear to us that "slang" is an integral part of the cultural layer. But it is worth noting that "slang" should not be confused with other layers of non-literary vocabulary, it is an independent phenomenon in the language.

Thus, under youth slang, we mean a set of constantly transforming linguistic means of high expressive power, which are used in the communication of young people consisting of familiar, friendly relations. There are several points of view related to the problem of allocation, without separating slang from a number of others, both as a concept and as a term in internal linguists. Some researchers deny the existence of slang. They attribute the existing slang words of different lexical and stylistic categories.

For example: I.R.Halperin in his article "About the term "slang", referring to the uncertainty of this category, usually denies its existence. His argument is based on the results of research by English lexicographers, mainly on their experience in compiling English dictionaries, which showed that the same word in different dictionaries has different linguistic recognition. The term "slang" in English means:

- the speech of a socially or professionally excluded group in contrast to the literary language;
- a variant of colloquial speech (including expressively colored elements of this speech) that do not coincide with the norm of the literary language. Slang consists of words and phraseological units that originated and were originally used in separate social groups. Slang reflected the holistic orientation of these groups. Having become common, these words mostly retain an emotional and evaluative character, although sometimes the "sign" of the evaluation changes.

Jargon synonym. Are there any other words you should look out for that have the same meaning as 'jargon'? Let's see...

Jargon doesn't have any exact synonyms. However, there are some other terms that mean similar things and could be used in place of the word 'jargon' in certain circumstances. Some examples include:

- **Lingo:** this is often used in place of the word 'slang', but if you added other words to it, such as 'botanical lingo', 'engineering lingo', or 'business lingo', then you get phrases that essentially mean *jargon*. It's worth noting that the term 'lingo' is quite colloquial, so it might not be appropriate to use in all situations.
- **-Speak** or **-ese:** similarly to 'lingo', these suffixes can be added to words to refer to the kind of vocabulary used in different professions. For instance, 'medical speak' (medical jargon) or 'legalese' (legal jargon).
- **Argot:** this is potentially one of the nearest synonyms for jargon and refers to the slang or specialised language used by a particular group (usually related to social factors such as age and class).
- **Patter:** this is a slang term that refers to jargon or the specific language used in certain occupations.

Jargon examples

To consolidate our understanding of what jargon is even further, we'll now look at some examples of jargon used in different professions.

Furthermore, as a result of our studies within the GS, the YS should also be worthy of its own characteristics, in which case we give it the following approach in Uzbek language: Slang is the language of (1) youth. It is kind of live communication to bring a spirit of novelty and modernity, to show fun and joy in order to move away from the old in exchange of information. It does not reflect any (2) bias and rude features. It is therefore genetically and functionally different from argot and vulgarism. (3) YS do not have professional limitations (this is large social group and not professional terms). This aspect is different from youth jargon. Due to time goes by, the vocabulary of YS will also be updated. Hence, its most significant feature (4) is novelty. Consequently, there exists a synonymy in slang. The old ones are replaced by new ones. Apart from this, it is characterized by semantic (5) humor. The context is used in the form of humor in order to avoid sadness and uninteresting atmosphere, and appear emotional-expressive conversation. It is a (6) word game of the younger generation a means to distinguish them from oldster. Furthermore, it has brightly expressed (7) emotional-evaluative character.

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